

6-Aldehydo-4-methyl- α -naphthapyrone and Dyes Derived from it.

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6-Aldehydocoumarin was previously obtained by the application of Reimer and Tiemann's reaction on coumarin (Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 2428). 4-Methyl- α -naphthapyrone similarly yields about 30% of an aldehyde, the aldehydic group entering the 6-position (*para* to original OH group) there being no other possibility. The aldehyde does not melt up to 300°, it readily gives a phenylhydrazone (m. p. 125°), a semicarbazone (m.p. 260°) and an oxime (which does not melt up to 260°).

The aldehyde condenses with dimethylaniline to produce a leuco base of a triphenylmethane dye which on oxidation gives the carbinol, the salt of which produces a bluish-green shade on silk and wool. A pyronine dye has been obtained by condensing the aldehyde with four molecules of resorcinol, when the C=O group in the lactone ring as well as the aldehyde group react. Silk is dyed a bright orange shade by the sodium salt of this compound.

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Aldehydo-4-methyl- α -naphthapyrone.

A solution of 4-methyl- α -naphthaypyrone (10.5 g.) (obtained by the condensation of α -naphthol and acetoacetic ester in presence of sulphuric acid, Bartsch, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1966) in caustic soda (14 g.

in 40 c.c. of water) was heated on the water-bath for 10-12 hours with gradual addition of a mixture of chloroform (10 c.c.) and alcohol (30 c.c.). The temperature was kept initially at 80° for the first 3 hours, the solution being mechanically stirred throughout. The deep red solution turned first deep blue on the addition of chloroform and alcohol and changed to red again after 6-7 hours. The solution, after removing alcohol and chloroform on a water-bath was acidified with acetic acid when a pasty gelatinous solid separated out. This was collected, dried, and washed several times with chloroform to remove any excess of the mother substance. The residue was dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) as brown microcrystalline needles, m.p. above 280°, yield 3.5 g.

It is insoluble in water, chloroform, benzene and ether; moderately soluble in alcohol and acetone and very readily soluble in hot glacial acetic acid. (Found: C, 74.78; H, 4.34. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 75.63; H, 4.2 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised as yellow needles from dilute acetic acid, m. p. 125°. (Found: N, 9.25. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.53 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual manner, separated as chocolate brown needles from dilute alcohol, m. p. 260°. (Found: N, 15.31, $C_{16}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires N, 14.23 per cent).

Oxime.—The aldehyde (2 g.) was dissolved in the smallest amount of dilute caustic soda solution and to this solution was added a saturated solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (5 g.) and the solution heated on a boiling water-bath with an air condenser for 4.5 hours. It was then cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitate dried. It crystallised from alcohol as red microcrystalline needles not melting below 280°. (Found: N, 5.54. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 5.53 per cent).

Condensation of the aldehyde with dimethylaniline.—The aldehyde (2 g.) was dissolved in dimethylaniline (10 c.c.) and the solution heated on a boiling water-bath for 30 hours with frequent additions of concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c. in all). It was isolated as usual and finally crystallised from alcohol as greenish-white powder not melting below 250°. It is moderately soluble in alcohol and acetone and soluble in both acid and alkali. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_{31}H_{30}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.06 per cent).

When the leuco base, thus obtained, is oxidised with lead peroxide, it dyes silk a beautiful greenish-blue shade.

Condensation of the Aldehyde with Resorcinol.

A mixture of the dry aldehyde (1 mol., 1.5 g.), dry resorcinol (4 mol., 5 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 2 c.c.) was heated first, in a boiling water-bath for 2-3 hours and then on an oil-bath at 120-130° for 5-6 hours with an air condenser. It was then isolated in the manner described by Sen and Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*).

The formula is based on the fact that the analogous condensation product of 6-aldehydro-coumarin with resorcinol possesses a similar formula giving a tripotassium salt (Sen and Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*). It does not melt below 280° and is soluble in alcohol and acetone, insoluble in ether and benzene. Silk is dyed a bright orange shade by its sodium salt. (Found: C, 77.16; H, 4.03. $C_{39}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 77.49; H, 3.97 per cent).

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